

Green Economy as a Mechanism of Sustainable Development

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Abstract: In world practice, special importance is attached to the sustainable development of regions, the study of their economic and ecological systems in mutually effective harmony. In particular, the development of countries directly depends on the stability of regions, and the positive aspects of this issue include the rational and effective use of resources based on the expansion of the innovative economy. The article describes the need and importance of the transition to a green economy, the structure of the green economy and its important features, its importance in the development of countries and in ensuring the stability of economic growth. The production of renewable energy sources, reduction of carbon emissions, and ensuring energy efficiency are discussed in detail.

Keywords: carbon dioxide, green economy, energy density, ecological changes, energy efficiency, climate change.

INTRODUCTION

Production of renewable energy sources, reduction of carbon emissions SO₂, increase of greenhouses with green technology, redevelopment and supply of water based on green technologies, "green" means of transport, electrification of cars, "green" households, production of clean ecological products in cities, the production of environmentally friendly, organic food in agriculture is important today. Formation of "green" economy and transition to its sustainable development is one of the priority tasks both at the global level and for Uzbekistan. The concept of sustainable development is an important resource for the future of humanity, and it is expressed in UN resolutions and documents. The economic and ecological basis of sustainable development is the formation and development of the "green" economy. In order to overcome the current unstable trends, in 2015 specific criteria of 17 "green" economic development goals of the UN for the period up to 2030 were defined. The decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 2, 2022 No. PQ-436 "On measures to increase the efficiency of reforms aimed at the transition of the Republic of Uzbekistan to a "green" economy by 2030" "Goals of the transition of Uzbekistan to a green economy were determined [1].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The article focuses on the need for a green economy, its features, the transition to a "green" economy in industries, and the provision of energy-saving electricity. Within the scope of conducting research in this direction, the results of a number of previous scientific researches were studied.

For example, M.A. Gureva in his researches has created a number of problems in the development of the "Green" economy, and introduced fines for having a negative impact on the environment as their solutions; reduce the release of toxic substances; mentioned the need to introduce the practice of restoring the damage caused to the environment. The implementation of

these measures will lead to an increase in the well-being and quality of life of the population. Green economy helps people to use environmentally friendly services and products [2].

The need to create a separate "Green" financing system arose due to the fact that environmental protection measures cannot be implemented without financial resources. That's why Bunevich K.G. and Gorbacheva T.A. In their research, they put forward the concepts of "Green Finance", "Green Investment". They suggested that new "Green" financial instruments are designed not only to obtain economic benefits from their use, but also to solve environmental and climate problems and protect it [3].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The concept of green economy emerged at the end of the 20th century and emphasizes the need to reduce the negative impact of human economic activity on the environment. In any case, beams are a trend that focuses on sustainable development, not on growth. it's tormenting. Supporters of this tendency believe that the economy is a dependent component of the natural environment in which it exists and is a part of it.

Important features of "green" economy include the following [4]:

- efficient use of natural resources;
- preservation and enrichment of natural capital;
- environmental pollution protection;
- transition to a low-carbon economy;
- recycling and turning waste into a resource;
- preservation of ecosystem services and biological diversity;
- ensuring income and employment;
- achieving energy efficiency in the economy, switching to the consumption of renewable energy sources.

Table 1. Energy capacity of economically developed countries (dj/\$)

Country	Years							Declining energy capacity trend %		
	2005	2007	2009	2010	2015	2025	2035	2015 2005	2025 2015	2025 2025
Russia	17,06	16,64	12,97	11,32	10,08	9,01	7,89	169,25	111,88	114,20
Canada	14,63	14,27	13,47	11,95	11,03	10,18	9,43	132,64	108,35	107,95
South Korea	13,43	13,27	10,31	8,55	7,76	7,14	9,28	173,07	108,68	76,94
USA	10,06	9,92	8,49	7,58	6,74	5,97	5,37	149,26	112,90	111,17
Australia and New Zealand	9,61	9,59	8,80	7,85	6,97	6,20	5,50	137,88	112,42	112,73
China	7,47	8,14	6,58	5,48	4,65	3,99	3,46	160,65	116,54	115,32
European Union	7,73	7,68	6,75	6,00	5,26	4,70	4,20	146,96	111,91	111,90
Japan	7,12	7,09	6,41	6,01	5,75	5,53	5,32	123,83	103,98	103,95
Mexico	7,03	6,85	6,78	6,16	5,58	4,97	4,44	125,99	112,27	111,94
Brazil	6,66	6,64	6,51	5,59	5,10	4,68	6,09	130,59	108,97	76,85
India	4,42	4,36	3,33	2,94	2,57	2,24	1,92	171,98	114,73	116,67

Transition to a "green" economy in industrial sectors and ensuring energy efficiency In the concept, energy capacity will be increased by 20% by saving 3.9 billion cubic meters of natural gas, 4 billion kWh of electricity and 21 thousand tons of oil products in industrial sectors, including 5% in 2023 tasks such as reduction were set.

It should be noted that air pollution is only one of the environmental factors that cause the premature death of 4.5 million people on our planet every year. The global economy was damaged by approximately 2.7 billion euros.

Increasing the efficiency of electricity use, providing cheap electricity and reducing the level of pollution is one of the problems in the energy sector (facing developing countries). In 2022, 1,285 million people around the world did not have access to electricity, and the issue of providing them with electricity remains a serious problem. In 2040, global electricity demand is expected to reach 40,104 GWh, which is about 1.8 times more than in 2022. The transition to the use of "clean coal" technologies, which allow the capture, storage, and use of carbon emissions, will lead to "deurbanization".

In this case, storing SO₂ emissions as a geological solution at a depth of 23 kilometers would be of great benefit, but it would require a large financial investment. If predicted energy consumption continues, annual SO₂ emissions will increase by around 40 Gt by 2040. As a result of this increase in SO₂ emissions, the average temperature of the earth is 3.6 increases from °C to 5.3 °C.

In the diagram below, you can see the energy consumption per capita by region and the data of our country.

It can be concluded from the above graphic data that the energy demand is the highest in the North American region (216.8 Dj in 2020), and the lower indicators correspond to the African region (13.9 Dj in 2020).

In Uzbekistan, this indicator was 56 Dj in 2020, and in general, it recorded a slightly decreasing trend.

Consequently, Uzbekistan also needs to change the methods of energy production and use. In the last 10 years, pilot projects should be developed on a large scale throughout the country.

Another common concept of the "green" economy is the low-carbon economy. The goal of low-carbon development is to reduce the emission of greenhouse gas emissions into the atmosphere. According to the opinions of many foreign scientists, the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions will lead to the stabilization of the global climate system. One way to achieve this goal is to improve energy efficiency. The main source of SO₂ emissions is the use of coal, oil, and gas. Currently, many countries and international corporations are reducing the use of coal, a significant source of greenhouse gas emissions. We can see the SO₂ emissions in the world through the diagram below.

In terms of carbon dioxide SO₂ emission into the atmosphere, China takes the first place with 28%, the USA takes the second place with 15%, India takes the third place with 7%, Germany takes the sixth place (the first place in Europe) with 2%, Brazil (in South America) is the main producer of carbon monoxide SO₂ gas. producer) occupies 1% and Australia 1%.

Regulation of SO₂ emissions is also of great importance in Uzbekistan, and the following directions can be mentioned [6]:

1. Regulation of the laws and system that should form the green energy market based on the conditions of Uzbekistan.
2. Government should invest in green technology and green business. Uzbekistan should develop carbon index and carbon standards.
3. The government should develop measures to organize energy and carbon exchanges and increase their efficiency.
4. The government needs to reform the tax and financial system to ensure green growth.
5. The government needs to improve the system of cooperation with authorities, companies, civil institutions and business to support green growth.

6. The government should study the global green growth trend and adopt a green national policy.
7. Environmental requirements investment should be included in the accounting procedure.
8. The climate change and global warming program covers 190 countries, and it is necessary to further activate the implementation of this program in Uzbekistan.
9. It is necessary to create a national system of greenhouse gas trade in Uzbekistan, as well as organize a national carbon index, carbon value and market.

CONCLUSION

The end result of the green economy is to eradicate poverty, achieve equality, increase the efficiency of resource use, attract investment, create new jobs, and increase access to new markets. Developed countries believe that the transition to a "green" economy should mean changing consumption and production models in industrialized countries, as well as combating the poverty economy. It is important to study the experience of the European Union, which is achieving sufficient success, with a clear understanding of the transition from the traditional model of economic growth to "green" economy modernization, concentration of resources and funds on priority innovative projects of competitive technologies.

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